

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online at :

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2issue-4-may-2014>

Email us: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

GO GREEN BY P³ – INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP TO TRANSFORM RURAL ECONOMY TOWARDS AFFLUENCE AND PROGRESSION

Dr. G.P. Dinesh

Dean – Department of Management Studies
Ballari Institute of Technology And Management
Jnana Gangotri Campus, Allipur [village]
Hospet road
Bellary – 583104. Karnataka

A.Mahesh

Research Scholar (VTU Belgaum),
Assistant Professor - Department of Management Studies
Ballari Institute of Technology And Management
Jnana Gangotri Campus, Allipur [village], Hospet road
Bellary – 583104. Karnataka

Abstract

India is an agrarian country, more than 60% of the population lives in the villages and rural areas, and the major occupation held by most of the people in rural India is agriculture and allied activities. Moreover the agriculture in India is considered as gamble with monsoon. More than 60% are dry lands; ironically the rainfall in India is not evenly distributed, which is a major bottle neck in the agri-output augmentation. It is very much necessary to transform dry lands into productive avenues of income & employment generation. It is the time to encourage the rural people to pursue the entrepreneurship as a means to overcome the barriers to growth and development & reduce the dependence on uncertain agriculture. Entrepreneurship is the only means by which we can transform the rural economy, ensure the

generation of employment, equitable distribution of income and wealth. On the other hand, India is facing severe energy crisis, imports are dominated by the crude oil and petroleum products. Moreover India is shedding huge amount of foreign exchange on oil imports to keep the country moving. Biodiesel from microalgae seem to be the most promising renewable biofuel that has the potential to completely displace petroleum-derived transport fuel without adversely affecting supply of food and other agricultural products. Demand for fuel never comes down; hence an Innovative entrepreneurshipⁱⁱ in this direction has high probability to succeed. To enunciate a study has been initiated to ascertain the potential of Micro Algae production and marketing at the rural areas and devising of a unique PPP(P³) – Public Private Partnership modelⁱⁱⁱ, which will ensure the optimum utilization of rural resources, generate the continuous employment for rural people, lessen the dependency on the uncertain agriculture, reduce the dependency on the fossil fuels, provide an alternative source of energy, decrease the environmental pollution, save precious foreign exchange and make India a self sufficient country.

Key Words: Innovative Entrepreneurship, Biofuel, Public Private Partnership, energy crisis.

Introduction

The energy crisis and the world food crisis have ignited interest in algaculture (farming algae) for making biodiesel and other biofuels using land unsuitable for agriculture. Among algal fuels attractive characteristics are that they can be grown with minimal impact on fresh water resources^{iv}, can be produced using saline and wastewater, have a high flash point^v, and are biodegradable and relatively harmless to the environment if spilled^{vi}. Algae cost more per unit mass than other second-generation biofuel crops due to high capital and operating costs^{vii}, but are claimed to yield between 10 and 100 times more fuel per unit area^{viii}. The United States Department of Energy estimates that if algae fuel replaced all the petroleum fuel in the United States, it would require 15,000 square miles (39,000 km²), which is only 0.42% of the U.S. map^{ix}, or about half of the land area of Maine. This is less than 1/7 the area of corn harvested in the United States in 2000. Microalgae are a diverse group of single-celled organisms that have the potential to offer a variety of solutions for our liquid transportation fuel requirements through a number of avenues. Algal species grow in a wide range of aquatic environments, from freshwater through saturated saline. Algae efficiently use CO₂, and are responsible for more than 40% of the global carbon fixation, with the majority of this productivity coming from marine microalgae. Algae can produce biomass very rapidly, with some species doubling in as few as 6 h, and many exhibiting two doublings per day. All algae have the capacity to produce energy-rich oils, and a number of microalgal species have been found to naturally accumulate high oil levels in total dry biomass. Algae grow much faster than food crops, and can produce hundreds of times more oil per unit area than conventional crops such as rapeseed, palms, soybeans, or [jatropha](#)^x. As algae have a harvesting cycle of 1–10 days, their cultivation permits several harvests in a very short time-frame, a strategy differing from that associated with annual crops^{xi}. In addition, algae can be grown on land unsuitable for terrestrial crops, including arid land and land with excessively saline soil, minimizing competition with agriculture^{xii}. Most research on algae cultivation has focused on growing algae in clean but expensive photo bioreactors, or in open ponds, which are cheap to maintain but prone to contamination^{xiii}. In comparison with terrestrial-based biofuel crops such as corn or soybeans, microalgal production results in a much less significant land footprint due to the higher oil productivity from the microalgae than all other oil crops^{xiv}. Algae can also be grown on marginal lands useless for ordinary crops and with low conservation value, and can use water from salt aquifers that is not useful for agriculture or drinking^{xv}. Thus microalgae could provide a source of clean energy with little impact on the provisioning of adequate food and water or the conservation of biodiversity^{xvi}. [105] Algae cultivation also requires no external subsidies of insecticides or herbicides, removing any risk of generating associated pesticide waste streams. Furthermore, compared to fuels like diesel and petroleum, the combustion of algal biofuel does not produce any sulfur oxides, and produces a reduced amount of carbon monoxide, unburned hydrocarbons, and reduced emission of harmful pollutants^{xvii}. Finally, algal biofuel consists of safe, natural compounds that represent little to no environmental risk if spilled, in contrast with fossil fuels

Course: The research problem is stated at point section-1; significance of the study is revealed at section-2; the objectives of the study are discussed at section-3; the methodology adopted by the researchers is depicted at section-4; data analysis is discussed at section-5; findings & conclusion from the study is stated at section-6; public private partnership model is discussed in section-7.

Section-1 Statement of the problem: Rural population is dependent on agriculture which is uncertain and gamble with monsoon; it is important to ensure consistent income for rural people to ensure overall growth. It is possible with agri-based rural entrepreneurship; contradictorily Indian import bill is always dominated by oil imports. Above all the environment is deteriorating due to burning of fossil fuels. Hence it is important to devise a unique rural entrepreneurship such that it uses rural unused resources, provide continuous employment to rural people, provide alternative energy, reduce the depletion of forex by heavy imports, protect environment with eco-friendly bio-fuel and ultimately make India a self reliant country. To overcome all the problems stated above, this study aims at devising a unique public private partnership model.

Section-2 Significance of the Study: This study connotes significant contribution in terms of employment generation to rural people, optimum utilization of available unused rural resources, developing alternative source of energy, reducing the import burden on Indian economy, protecting environment from global warming and making India a self reliant country.

Section-3 Objectives of the study

1. To understand the earning potential of the rural people pre and post harvest periods.
2. To create awareness about the micro-algae cultivation among the rural people.
3. To assess the preparedness of the people w.r.t. micro-algae cultivation.
4. To devise unique PPP model.

Section-4 Methodology

Four backward mandals from Kadapa district Andhra Pradesh, namely Vontimitta, Valluru, Chintakomma Dinne, and Veeranayunipalle has been chosen for the purpose of the study. Random sampling procedure was followed to select sample respondents from the sampling area, looking into convenience 15 respondents each were selected from four mandals, (4 X 15 = 60 is the sample size). The basic research design is based on primary source of data; however, secondary sources are also taken into consideration. Data were collected from the above respondents, using interview schedule specifically designed for the purpose; Tabulated data was analyzed with the help of statistical techniques such as, Correlation coefficients, Mean, Variance, Standard Deviation, Factor analysis and simple percentages. The questionnaire was structured using the theory of planned behavior (TPB) a social-psychological model which attempts to predict and understand people's behavior in specific contexts. The results were used to predict biofuel production given the farmers' willingness to provide raw materials. The implications for attainment of biofuel targets are discussed in light of these predictions. The main assumptions of TPB are that people behave rationally, their behavior is a function of the information or beliefs they have, and behavior is immediately preceded by behavioral intention. The greater the behavioral intention, the more likely it is an individual will perform the behavior. The individual weighs up all available information and influence; from personal instinct, policy, advisory services, the media, family, friends, and peers and forms their beliefs^{xviii}. Three aspects are considered to influence behavioral intention. Beliefs about the likely consequences of the behavior produce an attitude toward the behavior. Beliefs about others normative expectations result in perceived social pressure or subjective norm. Beliefs about the presence of give rise to perceived behavioral control^{xi}. Importantly, each aspect can be weighted, as behavioral intention is predicted to be influenced only by those aspects which are salient to the individual, and this may vary from person to person^{xx}.

FIGURE 1. The Theory of Planned Behavior (adapted from ref 13).

Figure 1 provides an overview of the theory. Attitude (A) toward a specific behavior is a measure of the degree to which it is positively or negatively valued. Attitude could be assessed directly by asking an individual whether a behavior is good or bad, or it can be determined indirectly using a set of behavioral beliefs, linking the behavior to various outcomes. Subjective norm (SN) is a measure of the perceived social pressure to engage or not to engage in a behavior. An individual's normative belief about social referent is weighted by his or her motivation to comply with social referent. Perceived behavioral control (PBC) is a measure of people's perceptions of their ability to perform a specific behavior. It can be measured directly by asking people how easy or difficult it would be to perform the behavior. PBC can also be determined using a set of control beliefs: beliefs about things that may facilitate or impede performance of the behavior. A large amount of literature discusses the development and application of TPB. Much applied research relies on the Assumption that behavioral intention is an accurate proxy for actual behavior, i.e., the actual behavior of individuals is not recorded. Empirical evidence suggests that this assumption holds; when behaviors pose no serious control issues, then behavioral intention is a good predictor of behavior. When behaviors are not completely of the subject's own volition then perceived behavioral control in addition to behavioral intention is an important predictor of actual behavior. TPB and the theory of reasoned action (TORA; which measures attitude and subjective norm but not perceived behavioral control) have recently been applied to several aspects of farmer decision making, including environmental management farm business management, and uptake of new technology. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) started as the Theory of Reasoned Action in 1980 to predict an individual's intention to engage in a behavior at a specific time and place. The theory was intended to explain all behaviors over which people have the ability to exert self-control. The key component to this model is behavioral intent; behavioral intentions are influenced by the attitude about the likelihood that the behavior will have the expected outcome and the subjective evaluation of the risks and benefits of that outcome. The TPB has been used successfully to predict and explain a wide range of health behaviors and intentions including smoking, drinking, health services utilization, breastfeeding, and substance use, among others. The TPB states that behavioral achievement depends on both motivation (intention) and ability (behavioral control). It distinguishes between three types of beliefs - behavioral, normative, and control. The TPB is comprised of six constructs that collectively represent a person's actual control over the behavior.

1. **Attitudes** - This refers to the degree to which a person has a favorable or unfavorable evaluation of the behavior of interest. It entails a consideration of the outcomes of performing the behavior.

2. **Behavioral intention** - This refers to the motivational factors that influence a given behavior where the stronger the intention to perform the behavior, the more likely the behavior will be performed.
3. **Subjective norms** - This refers to the belief about whether most people approve or disapprove of the behavior. It relates to a person's beliefs about whether peers and people of importance to the person think he or she should engage in the behavior.
4. **Social norms** - This refers to the customary codes of behavior in a group or people or larger cultural context. Social norms are considered normative, or standard, in a group of people.
5. **Perceived power** - This refers to the perceived presence of factors that may facilitate or impede performance of a behavior. Perceived power contributes to a person's perceived behavioral control over each of those factors.
6. **Perceived behavioral control** - This refers to a person's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behavior of interest. Perceived behavioral control varies across situations and actions, which results in a person having varying perceptions of behavioral control depending on the situation. This construct of the theory was added later, and created the shift from the Theory of Reasoned Action to the Theory of Planned Behavior.

Data analysis:**Table 1: Land Holding Distribution**

Total Land Holding	< 1 Acre	2-3 Acres	3-5 Acres	5-10 Acres	> 10 Acres	Total
No. of Respondents	19	9	4	5	3	40
Percentage (%)	48%	23%	11%	12%	6%	100%

Table 2: Distribution showing type of land held by the farmers

Type of Land Held	Irrigated Land	Dry Land	Wet Land	Delta (river belt)	Total
No. of Respondents	4	30	3	2	39
Percentage (%)	10%	76%	8%	5%	100%

Table 3: Number of crops cultivated each year

Number of Crops	Crop Holidays	One crop / year	Two crops / year	Three crops / year	Total
No. of Respondents	12	23	4	1	40
Percentage (%)	30%	58%	8%	4%	100%

Table 4: Employment opportunities of rural people in a year

Employment in a year	3 months	6 months	9 months	Throughout year	Total
No. of Respondents	19	15	3	3	40
Percentage (%)	48%	38%	8%	6%	100%

Table 5: Income opportunities post harvest period

Income post harvest	Good	Average	Poor	Total
No. of Respondents	6	15	19	40
Percentage (%)	14%	38%	48%	100%

Table 6: alternative sources of income available to rural people

Alternative income sources	Yes	No	Total
No. of Respondents	15	25	40
Percentage (%)	38%	62%	100%

Table 7: annual income of the rural people per annum

Number of Crops	< 10,000	10,000 – 20,000	20,000 – 50,000	> 50,000	Total
No. of Respondents	6	18	10	6	40
Percentage (%)	16%	44%	24%	16%	100%

Table 8: awareness about the micro algae cultivation

Awareness about Micro Algae	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Aware	1	1.5%
Not Aware	39	98.5%
Total	40	100%

Table 9: Distribution of Respondents w.r.t. attitudes / Behavioral Beliefs

	Improve Avg Profits	Decrease Stblty of Profits	Stable profits	Diversify farm	Allocate time and resources	Protection against volatilities
Extremely unlikely	--	--	--	--	--	--
Strongly unlikely	--	2.50%	2.50%	--	--	--
Moderately unlikely	--	7.50%	2.50%	--	--	--
Neutral	45%	47.50%	35%	20%	32.50%	17.50%
Moderately likely	35%	30%	55%	62.50%	65%	55%
Strongly likely	25%	12.50%	5%	2.50%	2.50%	25%
Extremely likely	--	--	--	--	--	2.50%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Mean	4.8	4.42	4.58	4.98	4.7	5.12
S.D	0.823	0.903	0.747	0.62	0.516	0.723
Var	0.677	0.815	0.558	0.384	0.267	0.522

Chart 1: Scree plot of Attitudes / behavioral beliefs

Table 10: Communalities of Attitudes / behavioral beliefs

	Initial	Extraction
Improve Avg Profits	1.000	.900
Decrease Stability of Profits	1.000	.740
Stable Profits	1.000	.855
Diversify Farm	1.000	.766
Allocate Time Resources	1.000	.758
Protection Volatilities	1.000	.899

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 11: Component Matrix^a

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Improve Avg Profits			-.632	
Decrease Stability of Profits	.703			
Stable Profits	.695			
Diversify Farm		.603		
Allocate Time Resources		.662		
Protection against Volatilities		.522		-.613

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. 4 components extracted

Table 12: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Improve Avg Profits			.933	
Decrease Stability of Profits				
Stable Profits	.912			
Diversify Farm		.682		
Allocate Time Resources		.837		
Protection Volatilities				.929

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. Rotation converged in 7 iterations

	Grwth Stblty	Avg Profit Low Stblty	Avg Prft high Stblty	Diversify farm	Equip time and resources	Will grow micro algae
Extremely unimportant	--	40%	--	--	--	--
Strongly unimportant	--	27.5%	--	--	--	--
Moderately unimportant	--	15%	--	--	--	--
Neutral	--	12.5%	--	12.5%	2.5%	27.5%
Moderately important	--	2.5%	30%	35%	12.5%	20%
Strongly important	30%	2.5%	55%	52.5%	42.5%	52.5%
Extremely important	70%	--	15%	--	42.5%	--
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Mean	2.70	1.82	1.85	1.40	2.25	1.25
S.D	.464	1.299	.662	.709	.776	.870
Var	.215	1.687	.438	.503	.603	.756

Chart 2: scree plot of behavioral outcome evaluations

	Initial	Extraction
Grwth Stblty	1.000	.780
Avg Prft Low Stblty	1.000	.767
Avg Prft High Stblty	1.000	.584
Diversifying Farm	1.000	.559
Equip Time Resources	1.000	.672
Will Grow MicroA lgae	1.000	.473

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

	Component		
	1	2	3
GrwthStblty			.760
AvgPrftLowStblty		.806	
AvgPrftHighStblty	.674		
DiversifyingFarm			.566
EquipTimeResources	-.520	.600	
WillGrowMicroAlgae	.636		

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
3 Components extracted.

	Component		
	1	2	3
GrwthStblty			.881
AvgPrftLowStblty		.840	
AvgPrftHighStblty	.699		
DiversifyingFarm	.684		
EquipTimeResources		.660	
WillGrowMicroAlgae	.636		

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

Table 17: Distribution of responses w.r.t Normative Beliefs (subjective & Social Norms)

	Family view	Peer view	Specialist view	Media view
Extremely disagree	--	2.5%	--	--
Strongly disagree	17.5%	65%	--	--
Moderately disagree	60%	32.5%	15%	--
Neutral	22.5%	--	55%	17.5%
Moderately agree	--	--	30%	57.5%
Strongly agree	--	--	--	25%
Extremely agree	--	--	--	--
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%
Mean	3.05	2.30	4.15	5.08
S.D	.639	.516	.662	.656
Var	.408	.267	.438	.430

Chart 3: Scree plot of normative beliefs

	Initial	Extraction
Family view	1.000	.712
Peer view	1.000	.617
Specialist view	1.000	.705
Media view	1.000	.471

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

	Component	
	1	2
familyview		.724
peerview	.786	
spealstview		.790
mediaview	-.674	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
a. 2 components extracted.

	Component	
	1	2
familyview		.763
peerview	.782	
spealstview		.759
mediaview	-.683	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Table 21: Distribution of respondent's agreements w.r.t. motivations to comply

	Always not required	Frequently not required	Occasionally not required	Neutral	Occasionally required	Frequently required	Always required	Total	Mean	S.D	Var
Family approval	--	--	20%	15%	15%	47.50%	2.50%	100%	4.98	1.25	1.563
Peer approval	--	20%	32.50%	15%	5%	27.50%	--	100%	3.88	1.52	2.317
Specialist approval	--	--	--	25%	30%	45%	--	100%	5.2	0.82	0.677
Media approval	--	35%	40%	20%	5%	--	--	100%	2.95	0.87	0.767

Chart 4: scree plot of motivations to comply

Table 22: Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Family approval	1.000	.842
Peer approval	1.000	.563
Specialist approval	1.000	.769
Media conformance	1.000	.696

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 23: Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
Family approval		.917
Peer approval	.691	
Specialist approval	.721	
Media conformance	.818	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
a. 2 components extracted.

Table 24: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
familyapproval		.890
peerapproval	.738	
specialistapproval	.596	.643
mediaconformance	.834	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Table 25: distribution of respondent’s agreements w.r.t. perceived control beliefs

Time spent on	0 – 13%	14 – 27%	28 – 41%	42 – 55%	55- 69%	70 – 83%	84 – 100%	Total	Mean	S.D	Variance
Farming activities	--	40%	60%	--	--	--	--	100%	2.6	0.496	0.246
Crops/livestock	--	--	--	--	45%	55%	--	100%	5.55	0.504	0.254

Table 26: Distribution of responses w.r.t. power of control factors

Time spent on	Extremely disagree	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Neutral	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Extremely agree	Total	Mean	S.D	Variance
Non-Farming Activities	--	--	--	10.30%	28.20%	43.60%	17.90%	100%	5.69	0.893	0.798
Other crops/livestock	--	--	--	--	2.60%	46.20%	51.30%	100%	6.49	0.556	0.309

Table 27: perceived control beliefs

	Never keep records	Very rarely	Moderately rarely	Can't tell	Moderately keep records	Frequently keep records	Always keep records	Total	Mean	S.D	Variance
Keep records	--	--	47.50%	--	--	52.50%	--	100%	5.52	0.506	0.256
Weed/erosion problem				52.50%	47.50%			100%	4.48	0.506	0.256

Table 28: Distribution of responses w.r.t. beliefs about trust in institutions

	Extremel y disagree	Stro ngly disa gree	Mode rately disagr ee	Neutra l	Moder ately agree	Strong ly agree	Extre mely agree	Total	Mea n	S.D	Var
Govt Role Determines success	--	--	--	--	47.50%	52.50%	--	100%	5.52	0.506	0.256
Energy Cos. Help farmers	--	--	--	52.50%	47.50%	--	--	100%	4.48	0.506	0.256
Require Govt Support	--	--	--	--	--	35%	65%	--	8.38	10.97	120.49

Findings

Land holding is very low because of sub-division and fragmentation. About 48 % of the rural people are having less than 1 acre land holding. 90% of the lands are dry and rain fed, the irrigation facilities are very nominal. 30 % of the people have declared crop holidays; 58 % of the people are cultivating only one crop per year. The rain fall is very scanty. The fertility of the soil is very low. Majority people’s annual income is less than or equal to 20,000. The employment opportunities are not uniformly round the year; around 49% of respondents expressed they have employment only for 3 months. About 61% of the respondents expressed they do not have any alternative source of income. Only 1.5% respondents are aware about micro algae cultivation. About 52.50% believed that government’s participation determines the success of micro algae cultivation. About 52.5% were neutral and 47.50% respondents moderately agreed about the energy companies extend their help to farmers to overcome initial hurdles. Over 65% of the respondents were expecting the support from the government to take up the cultivation of micro algae as a energy crop.

Findings - Factor analysis:

a) Scree plots:

The scree plot is a graph of the eigenvalues against all the factors. The graph is useful for determining how many factors to retain. The point of interest is where the curve starts to flatten. In **Chart 1:** It can be seen that the curve begins to flatten between factors 3 and 4. So, only four factors have been retained. **Chart 2:** reveals that the curve begins to flatten between factors 2 and 3. So, only three factors have been retained. **Chart 3:** reveals that the curve begins to flatten between factors 1 and 2. So, only two factors have been retained. **Chart 4:** reveals that the curve starts to flatten between 1 and 2 hence only two factors are retained.

b) Communalities table

Table of communalities which shows how much of the variance in the variables has been accounted for by the extracted factors. **Table 10:** reveals that over 90% of the variance in Micro algae cultivation improves average profit & protection against volatilities is accounted for while 85% of the variance in micro algae cultivation offers stable profits is accounted for. **Table 14:** reveals the variances in the variables accounted for extracted factors with respect to behavioral outcome evaluations. Over 78% of the variance in micro algae cultivation offers growth and stability in profits is accounted for while 85% of the variance in micro algae cultivation offers average profit and low stability is accounted for. **Table 18:** reveals the variances with respect to normative beliefs. Over 71% variance in family view is accounted for, where as 70% of variance is accounted for in specialist view. **Table 22:** reveals the variances regarding the motivations to comply: over 84% of variance is accounted for family approval in selection of a crop. Over 76% of the variance is accounted for in specialist approval is required for crop selection.

c) Component (Factor) Matrix

The table below shows the loadings of the variables on the factors extracted. The higher the absolute value of the loading, the more the factor contributes to the variable. The gap on the table represent loadings that are less than 0.5, this makes reading the table easier. We suppressed all loadings less than 0.5.

d) Rotated Component (Factor) Matrix

The idea of rotation is to reduce the number factors on which the variables under investigation have high loadings. Rotation does not actually change anything but makes the interpretation of the analysis easier. Looking at the **Table 12**: we can see that protection against market price volatilities is substantially loaded on factor 4, micro algae cultivation improves average profits of farmers is substantially loaded on Factor (Component) 3; while micro algae cultivation diversifies farm and allocation of time and resources are optimum are substantially loaded on Factor 2.

the remaining variable is substantially loaded on Factor 1. **Table 16**: we can see that growth and stability of profits is substantially loaded on factor 3, average profit-low stability and equipment, time and resources are substantially loaded on Factor (Component) 2; while all the remaining variables are substantially loaded on Factor 1. **Table 20**: we can see that family view and specialist view are in selection of crops are substantially loaded on factor 2, while all the remaining variables are substantially loaded on Factor 1. **Table 24**: we can see that family approval and specialist approval are in selection of crops are substantially loaded on factor 2, while all the remaining variables are substantially loaded on Factor 1.

Conclusion and Recommendations

By the survey, it is clear; the rural economy is affected badly by uncertain, irregular and inadequate monsoons, uneven distribution of land holdings and partial employment opportunities in a year. Thus it is further more important to incentivize the entrepreneurship among the rural people, as it paves a path to consistent income round the year, optimum utilization of the unused rural resources, reduces the dependence on uncertain agricultural income and employment. In hostile conditions where agriculture is no more viable, paradigm shift towards a energy source micro algae is necessary. As it can survive antagonistic conditions and provides alternative source of energy. Suitable strategies have been suggested in the form of Public Private Partnership model to eradicate the negative effects of these identified factors on the rural economy are as follows:

Public Private Partnership Model to cultivate Micro Algae as an Energy Crop

Objectives of the PPP Model:

- The model aims at maintaining the good infrastructure,
- Enhancing the cultivation and supply of micro algae,
- Creating year round employment and earning opportunities for the rural people,
- Most advantageous use of unemployed rural resources, Provide alternative source of energy, Reduce dependence on uncertain agriculture,
- Save precious foreign exchange by reducing the oil imports and ,
- Reduce the dependence on fossil fuels and make India self sufficient country.

Proposed Project Structure:

A partnership between, private and public sectors, where the private sector is responsible for providing certain facilities and services. In return, the public sector pays for these facilities and services, with the payment linked to the private sector's performance and benchmarked against the public sector's own previous cost in providing these facilities and services. The contract could be structured over 10–15 years.

Private Sector Role:

[i] Initial stage: Identification of the target growing areas by scanning the following :

- Cultivable wastelands / vacant lands / colliery wastelan
- Rain fed lands (low rainfall zone / rain shadow areas)
- Water scarcity areas
- Jhum fallows in Hilly areas
- Riverside that is not inundated
- Erosion prone watershed area

- Replacing uneconomical crops

[ii] Second stage:

Create awareness among the people about micro algae.
Create awareness regarding the immense demand for bio diesel,
Create awareness about the immense earning potential.
Hire and Train the rural people in cultivation of micro algae.
Establish training centers, information centers and other related infrastructural facilities.
Divide people into groups for effective implementation of the planned activities.

[iii] Third stage:

- Effective fencing and refurbishment of the cultivation area.
- Land preparation, bed formation, digging of pits and filling by cow dung etc.
- Scientific maintenance of the crop.
- Setting up of equipments and maintenance of the equipments, (water pumps, pipelines, motors, & sprinklers).
- Systematic varietal improvement & hybridization programme
- Generation of technology for yield enhancement
- Technologies related to value addition of byproducts
- Demonstration of technologies through Model Farms / Focused Extension programme
- Mass multiplication of elite plant material through tissue culture.
- Provision of information management and technology solutions.
- Facilities management such as cleaning, waste disposal, pesticides management etc.

[iv] Fourth stage:

- Establish a contract farming agreement with oil refineries, in order to ensure the predictable rate for the output produced and ensure market access. Contract farming agreements with refineries, like, MRPL – Mangalore Refineries and Petro Chemicals Limited, Reliance Jamnagar Refineries etc. Scientific harvesting and packing of the produce, by using effective quality control techniques.

Public Sector Role

[a] Fund the Research for achieving the following needs-

1. Screening and development of strains / varieties, high yielding yet tolerant to hostile climatic conditions.
2. Standardization of growing areas for different terrain.
3. Practices for maximum yield
4. Manurial and fertilizer requirement
5. Use of lipid content enhancing hormones

[ii] Benchmarking :

Government sets performance parameters for the private sector player's role, monitors these parameters, and makes payments as per contract.

Technical issues

- The public sector authority signs a contract with a private sector "operator;"
- During the period of the contract, the operator will provide certain facilities and services.
- The operator is paid for the work over the course of the contract and on a "no service no fee" performance basis;
- The procuring authority will design an "output specification," which is a document setting out what the operator is expected to achieve;

- If the operator fails to meet any of the agreed standards, it would lose an element of its payment until standards improve;
- If standards do not improve after an agreed period, the public sector authority is entitled to terminate the contract.

The Financial plan key principles include:

Commencement of payment only on completion of the land preparation phase & commissioning of the cultivation and equipments. In case of phased completion, payment triggers are set at the end of each phase. Private sector is entitled to an annual charge on the commissioning of the entire plantation facility. The payment mechanism provides for deduction due to performance shortfalls.

Potential private sector players expected to respond

- Existing bio-diesel Manufacturing companies. Giant Corporations in agriculture and ailed businesses like, Tata Rallis, Bayer Crop Science, Monsanto, bio plant tech companies etc.
- Giant Corporations with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives can also join hands.
- NGO's aimed at rural development and women empowerment.
- Specialized private companies – Horticulture, Plantation, irrigation, construction, etc.
- Large construction and service provider companies.

Expected outcomes of the project

- Improved supply & availability of the micro algae for bio-diesel production.
- Yearlong employment for the rural people.
- Improved and consistent earning for rural people.
- Most advantageous utilization of the unused rural resources.
- Reducing the dependency on uncertain agriculture and uneconomical crops^{xxii}.
- Reduction in dependency on fossil fuels and save precious foreign exchange by abridged imports.
- Improved efficiencies—in both delivering micro algae on demand as well as in facilities maintenance and management.
- Increased private sector investments (upfront investments, which are paid back on an annuity basis).

Value Addition from Developmental banks or Consultancy Firms

Consultancy Firms or Developmental Banks can assist in the following ways:

- Transaction advisory assistance and provision for funding.
- Develop a detailed financial analysis, including analysis of typical capital and operating cost Investment levels of private sector, existing state budgets, potential for user charging, and consequently, affordability gap analysis.
- Understand the potential for use of central government schemes such as viability gap funding Or annuity model to support the financial and economic viability of this scheme.
- Develop a detailed output specification including the specification of cultivation, equipment, Standards, maintenance levels, and operating and/or performance levels.
- Assist in contracting process including bids, legal negotiations, and financial closure.
- Confirm legal position on provision of BEM contracts.

Proposed processing stages and timelines

- States agree to undertake the pilot: Month 1
- Appointment of transaction advisory: Month 4
- PPP structuring: By Month 7
- Bidding process: Months 8–10
- Finalizing the PPP contract: Month 14.
- starting the cultivation and growing of the micro algae: Month 15

End Notes / References

- ⁱ www.ethanolindia.net/algae_biodiesel.html - www.mnre.gov.in/ - Ministry of new and renewable energy – India.
- ⁱⁱ According to the OECD, innovation is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service) or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization or external relations of a company.
- ⁱⁱⁱ Involvement of private enterprise (in the form of management expertise and/or monetary contributions) in the government projects aimed at public benefit. PPP broadly refers to long term, contractual partnerships between public and private sector agencies, specially targeted towards financing, designing, implementing, and operating infrastructure facilities services that were traditionally provided by the public sector.
- ^{iv} Yang, Jia; Ming Xu; Xuezhong Zhang; Qiang Hu; Milton Sommerfeld; YongShen Chen (2010). "Life-cycle analysis on biodiesel production from microalgae: Water footprint and nutrients balance". *Bioresources Technology* **10**: 1016.
- ^v Dinh, L. T. T.; Guo, Y.; Mannan, M. S. (2009). "Sustainability evaluation of biodiesel production using multicriteria decision-making". *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy* **28**: 38. doi:10.1002/ep.10335.
- ^{vi} Demirbas, A. (2011). "Biodiesel from oilgae, biofixation of carbon dioxide by microalgae: A solution to pollution problems". *Applied Energy* **88** (10): 3541. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.12.050.
- ^{vii} Carriquiry, M. A.; Du, X.; Timilsina, G. R. (2011). "Second generation biofuels: Economics and policies". *Energy Policy* **39** (7): 4222. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2011.04.036.
- ^{viii} Greenwell, H. C.; Laurens, L. M. L.; Shields, R. J.; Lovitt, R. W.; Flynn, K. J. (2009). "Placing microalgae on the biofuels priority list: A review of the technological challenges". *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* **7** (46): 703. doi:10.1098/rsif.2009.0322.
- ^{ix} Hartman, Eviana (6 January 2008). "A Promising Oil Alternative: Algae Energy". *The Washington Post*. Retrieved 10 June 2008.
- ^x Atabani, A. E.; Silitonga, A. S.; Badruddin, I. A.; Mahlia, T. M. I.; Masjuki, H. H.; Mekhilef, S. (2012). "A comprehensive review on biodiesel as an alternative energy resource and its characteristics". *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **16** (4): 2070. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2012.01.003
- ^{xi} Chisti, Y. (2007). "Biodiesel from microalgae". *Biotechnology Advances* **25** (3): 294–306. doi:10.1016/j.biotechadv.2007.02.001. PMID 17350212
- ^{xii} Schenk, P. M.; Thomas-Hall, S. R.; Stephens, E.; Marx, U. C.; Mussgnug, J. H.; Posten, C.; Kruse, O.; Hankamer, B. (2008). "Second Generation Biofuels: High-Efficiency Microalgae for Biodiesel Production". *BioEnergy Research* **1**: 20. doi:10.1007/s12155-008-9008-8
- ^{xiii} Mata, T. M.; Martins, A. N. A.; Caetano, N. S. (2010). "Microalgae for biodiesel production and other applications: A review". *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **14**: 217. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2009.07.020.
- ^{xiv} Smith, V. H.; Sturm, B. S. M.; Denoyelles, F. J.; Billings, S. A. (2010). "The ecology of algal biodiesel production". *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* **25** (5): 301. doi:10.1016/j.tree.2009.11.007
- ^{xv} Bullis, Kevin (2007-02-05). "Algae-Based Fuels Set to Bloom | MIT Technology Review". *Technologyreview.com*. Retrieved 29 November 2013.
- ^{xvi} Groom, M. J.; Gray, E. M.; Townsend, P. A. (2008). "Biofuels and Biodiversity: Principles for Creating Better Policies for Biofuel Production". *Conservation Biology* **22** (3): 602. doi:10.1111/j.1523-1739.2007.00879.x. PMID 18261147
- ^{xvii} Hemaiswarya, S.; Raja, R.; Carvalho, I. S.; Ravikumar, R.; Zambare, V.; Barh, D. (2012). "An Indian scenario on renewable and sustainable energy sources with emphasis on algae". *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* **96** (5): 1125–1135. doi:10.1007/s00253-012-4487-0. PMID 23070650
- ^{xviii} Ajzen, I. From Intentions to Actions: A theory of Planned Behaviour. In *Action-Control: From Cognition to Behaviour*; Kuhl, J., Beckmann, J., Ed.; Springer: Heidelberg, 1985; pp 11-39.
- ^{xix} Ajzen, I. Perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the theory of planned behavior. *J. Appl. Social Psychol.* 2002, **32**, 665-683.
- ^{xx} Armitage, C. J.; Christian, J. From attitudes to behaviour: Basic and applied research on the Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Curr. Psychol.* 2003, **22**, 187-195.
- ^{xxi} Colliery lands means waste lands formed by mining activities.
- ^{xxii} The crops which are unviable in terms of investment and output, in which farmers do not recover ROI. Theory of planned behavior <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/journals.htm?articleid=1455229>
<http://pages.bangor.ac.uk/~pes004/resmeth/dataman/spss12/dataman2.htm>
Armitage CJ & Conner M. (2001). Efficacy of the Theory of Planned Behaviour: A meta-analytic review. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, **40**, 471-499.

- Ajzen, I. (1985). From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behaviour. In J Kuhl, J Beckman (Eds), *Action control: From cognition to behaviour* (pp. 11-39). New York: Springer.
- Ajzen, I. (1988). *Attitudes, personality and behaviour*. Milton Keynes; OUP.
- Ajzen I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211.
- Ajzen I. (2003). Website: <http://www-unix.oit.umass.edu/%7Eaizen/>
- Cohen J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis* (2nd ed.). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Conner M, Sparks P. (1995). The Theory of Planned Behaviour and health behaviours. In M Conner, P Norman (Eds), *Predicting health behaviour* pp. 121-162. Buckingham: OUP.
- Everitt, B. (1996). *The Cambridge dictionary of statistics in the medical sciences*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Fishbein M. (1967). Attitude and the prediction of behavior. In M Fishbein (Ed.), *Readings in attitude theory and measurement*. New York: Wiley.
- Gagné C, Godin G. (1999). Les théories sociales cognitives: Guide pour la mesure des variables développement de questionnaire. Groupe de recherché sure les aspects psychosociaux de la santé, École des sciences infirmieres, Université Laval.
- Godin G, Kok G. (1996). The Theory of Planned behaviour: A review of its applications to health-related behaviours. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 11(2), 87-98.
- Jones TV, Gerrity MS, Earp J. (1990). Written case simulations: Do they predict physicians' behaviour? *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 43, 805-815.
- McColl E, et al. (2001). Design and use of questionnaires: A review of best practice applicable to surveys of health service staff and patients. *Health Technology Assessment Methodology*, v. 5, no. 31; Alton: Core Research on behalf of the NCCHTA.
- Moser CA, Kalton G. (1993). *Social methods in social investigation* (2nd ed). Aldershot, Hants, England: Dartmouth Publishing Co.
- Popper K. (1974). *Unended quest: An intellectual autobiography* (updated edition 1992). London: Routledge.
- Seale C. (1998). (ed.) *Researching society and culture*. London : Sage.
- Tabachnick BG, Fidell LS. (2001). *Using Multivariate Statistics* (4th Ed). Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Valois P, Godin G. (1991). The importance of selecting appropriate adjective pairs for measuring attitude based on the semantic differential method. *Quality and Quantity*, 25, 57-68.
- Walker AE, Grimshaw JM, Armstrong EM. (2001). Salient beliefs and intentions to prescribe antibiotics for patients with a sore throat. *British Journal of Health Psychology*, 6, 347-360.